

Financial Landscape Analysis 2026

Scholarly Publishing &
Research Analytics
Companies

June 2026

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<https://doi.org/10.82513/px9c-q310>

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ABOUT THIS REPORT

Since 2019, SPARC has regularly provided our community with financial analyses of the four major companies active in scholarly journal publishing, research communications, and research data analytics. These companies play a critical role in the scholarly publishing landscape. RELX, Springer Nature Group (SNG), and Wiley are the three largest journal publishers, collectively accounting for 50% of articles published and between 52% and 58% of journal revenues. Clarivate is the leading provider of citation data, with a market share by revenue of 50 to 60%.

Since SPARC's last update in 2021, significant changes have occurred in the social, political, and economic landscape. The past 18 months have seen currency devaluation, significant uncertainty around federal research funding, and the rapid emergence of generative AI and large language models. Within the industry, major developments have included the completion of Springer Nature Group's IPO in October 2024.

SPARC commissioned market analyst Claudio Aspesi to analyze the current market performance of these four companies in light of these developments. This report provides a financial analysis based on publicly available market data, company filings, investor presentations, and interviews. It begins with a comparative overview of all four companies' financial performance, followed by detailed analyses examining each company's share price trajectory, operating results, management guidance, and strategic positioning. Supporting data tables appear in the appendix. A glossary of financial terms is included at the end. Additional supporting resources and insights are available to SPARC members.

SPARC members will directly receive an additional resource providing implications for institutions of the trends described in this analysis. If you would like access to this resource, please contact SPARC directly.

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During the preparation of this report, the authors used Claude Opus 4.7 in order to edit the document for readability and concision. After using this tool, the authors thoroughly reviewed and edited the text and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The four largest companies in scholarly publishing and research data analytics—RELX, Springer Nature Group, Wiley, and Clarivate—reported strong financial performance between October 2024 and March 2026. Across nearly every measure, revenue grew, margins expanded, and cash flow increased. Yet share prices for all four fell significantly over the same period. When investors pay less per dollar of earnings despite improving results, it generally signals doubt about long-term prospects.

The AI investment gap

The evidence points to AI as the primary driver of investor skepticism. Management at all four companies has argued in investor presentations that AI will benefit financial performance, but capital spending has not increased. Three of the four companies cut investment in 2025: SNG by 8.8%, Wiley by 11.8%, and Clarivate by 9%. RELX held investment flat at roughly 5% of revenues, the same benchmark that prevailed 20 years ago.

The gap between management's promises and the reality of capital investment levels creates three risks that investors are pricing in. First, demand could shrink due to competition from external AI services or reductions in the research workforces that hold licenses and subscriptions. Second, dependence on external AI infrastructure providers whose pricing is widely expected to rise creates cost pressure these companies may struggle to offset. Third, the productivity gains management is promising remain uncertain in both value and timeline, and the AI transition itself is likely to introduce costs before any gains materialize.

What this means for institutions

For institutions that rely on these companies for research infrastructure, current AI tool pricing should be understood as introductory. These companies face rising infrastructure costs that will likely be passed through, and institutions should plan accordingly.

At the same time, strong current financial performance at these companies is relevant for current negotiations. Declining stock prices reflect investor concerns about future AI risks, not deteriorating fundamentals. These companies have returned billions to shareholders: RELX returned £4.85 billion (about \$6.295 billion) through buybacks and dividends over the past two years, Clarivate \$462.2 million, Wiley \$258.4 million, and SNG €26.8 million (about \$30.8 million). Management at all four companies has issued positive guidance for 2026, with most projecting both revenue growth and margin expansion.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

This section presents a comparative financial analysis of the four largest companies in scholarly publishing and research data analytics—RELX, Springer Nature Group, Wiley, and Clarivate—covering the period October 2024 to March 2026.

Strong underlying performance

In 2025, all four companies reported strong financial results. Organic revenue grew at RELX (7%), SNG (6.2%), and Wiley (3%). Clarivate was effectively flat (-0.1%). Operating margins improved across most companies: RELX's group adjusted operating margin reached 34.8%, up from 33.9% in 2024. SNG's improved from 27.7% to 28.2%. Wiley recovered strongly from the 2024 Hindawi shutdown to reach 24.0%. At the research division level—the core business for three of the four companies—margins rose at RELX (Elsevier to 38.1%), SNG (Research to 32.1%), and Wiley (Research to 34.7%). Even Clarivate's Academia & Government division improved its margin to 43.3%, despite group-level compression.

Free cash flow¹ grew at all four companies: RELX up 9%, SNG up 36%, Wiley up 11%, and Clarivate up 2%. Three of the companies maintained debt ratios in a comfortable range of 1.7x to 2.0x Net Debt/EBITDA. Clarivate remained the outlier at 4.1x, but the ratio held stable.

¹ See glossary.

Organic revenue growth
2024 - 2025

Free cash flow growth
2024 - 2025

Research division operating margin change
2024 - 2025
Units in percentage points

Sources: Tables 3, 5 and 6. *Wiley data covers the first 4 months of 2025. Research division margin improvement reflects partial recovery from the Hindawi journal retraction period.

Management guidance for 2026 projects continued to improve. RELX expects strong growth in underlying revenues and operating profit. SNG projects 5–6% underlying revenue growth and margin expansion of 30 basis points. Wiley expects low single-digit revenue growth, an adjusted EBITDA margin of 25.5% to 26.5%, and free cash flow of approximately \$200 million. Clarivate projects 1.5% growth in recurring revenues and free cash flow of approximately \$400 million.

With a rising proportion of multi-year contracts and declining transactional revenues, near-term revenue at all four companies is relatively predictable. Subscription-based businesses have historically been insulated from economic downturns, which supports management’s positive 2026 guidance.

Declining share prices

Despite these results, share prices fell significantly over the same period. Between October 2024 and March 2026, RELX shares declined 30.2% while the FTSE 100 rose 22%. SNG has traded above its IPO placement price of €22.50 for fewer than 25% of trading days since listing. Wiley shares declined 21.7% while the S&P 500 rose 14.4%. Clarivate continued a longer decline, falling 61.6% over the period against a 13.4% rise in the S&P 500.

COMPANY SHARE PRICES: OCTOBER 2024 - MARCH 2026

*The MSCI World Index is a market capitalization-weighted index of about 1300 large and medium cap stocks across 23 countries and is used to provide a benchmark for the performance of stocks across all developed markets.

For RELX, SNG, and Wiley, the decline came in two distinct phases. The first, in Q4 2024 and Q1 2025, brought declines ranging from 15% to 41% peak to trough. Currency movements explain part of this: the dollar declined 12% against the Euro and 9% against the British Pound between January and June 2025, reducing expected profits at RELX and SNG. The decline was short-lived. By May and early June 2025, RELX was trading at its highest share price ever, SNG had recovered close to its IPO price, and Wiley was back at December 2024 levels.

The second decline, beginning in late June 2025, was deeper and more sustained. Between July 2025 and March 2026, share prices fell 33% to 51% from their peaks. Currency is not a plausible explanation: the dollar declined only 2.5% against the Euro and actually gained 0.6% against the British Pound. The sustained nature of the decline, combined with its disconnection from currency movements and its timing against improving operating results, points to more fundamental concerns about these companies' long-term prospects.

Clarivate’s pattern is distinct. From a peak of \$30.99 in September 2020, shares fell almost continuously to \$2.53 by March 2026, a 91.6% decline over five years. The factors driving this decline—management turnover, expensive acquisitions, strategic drift, and a heavy debt load coming due in 2028 and 2029—are specific to Clarivate, though the concerns affecting the other three companies apply here as well.

Share prices have recovered some ground since mid-February 2026, possibly reflecting a change in investor sentiment triggered by management’s increased focus on AI opportunities in recent presentations. Whether this represents a sustained shift or a temporary rally remains to be seen.

The investment gap and uncertainty about AI

Every recent investor presentation from all four companies makes the same argument: AI will benefit financial performance, and management has a plan to capture those benefits. Capital investment tells a different story. Three of the four companies cut investment in 2025: SNG by 8.8%, Wiley by 11.8%, Clarivate by 9%. RELX held flat at approximately 5% of revenues, the same benchmark that prevailed twenty years ago. The pattern holds across the sector.

CAPITAL INVESTMENT AS PERCENTAGE OF REVENUES, 2025

The 5% benchmark line represents the historical industry standard from approximately 2005. Clarivate's higher rate reflects catch-up spending to compensate for underinvestment by prior owners.

This gap between management's projections and capital investment levels is the most plausible explanation for sustained investor skepticism despite strong operating results. It creates three specific risks.

The first is revenue displacement. AI tools could reduce demand for publisher products directly through competing services, or indirectly by reducing the research workforces that hold institutional licenses. Publishers that have licensed content to external AI platforms face an additional version of this risk: those platforms may compete with the publishers' own AI tools. Wiley's AI Gateway, for instance, faces competition not only from LeapSpace and Nature Research Assistant but from other platforms with licensed access to Wiley content.

The second is cost pressure from infrastructure providers. These companies are building AI tools on infrastructure from OpenAI, Google, and Anthropic. These providers have priced aggressively to gain adoption but face pressure to recover substantial capital outlays. As they shift toward profitability, the pricing they charge publishers is widely expected to rise. Flat internal investment creates dependency on external providers at the moment when those providers' pricing power is increasing.

The third is uncertainty about productivity gains. Management at all four companies projects operational efficiency improvements from AI. The timeline and magnitude of those gains remain undemonstrated, and the transition itself introduces costs before any benefits materialize.

Company-specific positioning

RELX is the largest and most diversified, with the highest research division margins (38.1%) and the strongest cash generation. The company returned £4.85 billion (about \$6.295 billion) to shareholders through buybacks and dividends over the two-year period covered by this analysis—£1.5 billion in buybacks in 2025 alone, up 50% from 2024—even as it held capital investment steady at 5% of revenues. Management is positioning LeapSpace, an AI productivity tool for researchers, as a major growth driver, with an addressable market spanning all institutions where RELX has any existing tools or subscriptions.

SNG is the most concentrated of the four companies, with research accounting for 79% of revenue and 89% of operating profit. The research business has been gaining share against Elsevier, growing faster on both revenue and operating profit. But SNG's smaller scale is a structural disadvantage as the industry builds out AI capabilities. It invests 7.6% of revenue, a higher share than RELX or Wiley, but also cut total investment by 8.8% in 2025.

Wiley is the smallest of the three research publishers, with a research business about two-thirds the size of SNG's. It faces the greatest competitive disadvantage from scale constraints. The company returned to profitability in 2025 after the Hindawi shutdown, but most of that swing—\$69 million of an \$84 million profit—was driven by currency movements rather than underlying business performance. Wiley's aggressive content licensing strategy, designed to support revenue growth, creates its own form of competition. AI Gateway, Wiley's productivity tool, will likely face competition not only from LeapSpace and Nature Research Assistant but also from other platforms with direct access to Wiley content.

Clarivate faces challenges that extend beyond AI. The company carries \$4.4 billion in debt, including two \$900 million bond repayments due in July 2028 and July 2029. Bonds are rated three levels below investment grade, and the existing bonds carry low coupons, creating meaningful refinancing risk if rates remain elevated. Investors have fled the stock for reasons including management turnover, expensive acquisitions, strategic drift, and looming debt refinancing. The AI concerns raised for the other companies apply to Clarivate as well, compounded by its debt load and falling EBITDA, which leave it less able than its peers to invest in AI at competitive scale.

COMPANY ANALYSIS

The comparative analysis documents a pattern that holds across all four companies: strong operating performance, declining share prices, and capital investment that has not increased to match management's stated AI ambitions. The sections that follow examine each company individually, with the same questions in view: how has the share price moved and what explains it, how is the core research business performing, what is management projecting, and where are there uncertainties for investors.

RELX

Share price performance

In the first three years after SPARC's 2021 Landscape Analysis update, RELX shares outperformed the FTSE 100 significantly. Between October 1, 2021 and September 30, 2024, the share price grew by 64.4% (from £21.70 to £35.68), against 18.4% growth in the FTSE 100 over the same period. Including dividends, RELX's total return was 74.6%.

That picture reversed in the period covered by this report. Between October 1, 2024 and March 31, 2026, RELX shares fell 30.2% (from £35.46 to £24.76), while the FTSE 100 rose by 22%. Total returns show a similar gap: RELX declined by 29% while the FTSE 100 rose 23%. Like SNG and Wiley, this period contained two distinct phases of decline for RELX. The first, in early 2025, was relatively shallow: RELX shares peaked at £41.35 on February 13, 2025, and fell to £35.17 by April 7, a 14.9% decline. Currency movements can account for about 26% of that drop with the balance attributable to other factors not necessarily related to Elsevier or scholarly publishing. Shares then recovered, reaching £41.21 on May 2, 2025, before a deeper and more sustained decline began. By March 31, 2026 the share price had fallen 39.9% from its May peak. The dollar actually rose by 1.3% over this period, ruling out currency as an explanation. The second decline appears attributable to concerns about the performance of the business.

Operating performance

Group performance

RELX published its 2025 results in February 2026. The company posted strong results: underlying revenue grew 7%, underlying operating profit grew 9%, and adjusted EPS at constant currency grew 10%. The group adjusted operating profit margin reached 34.8%. Adjusted cash flow grew by 6.4% and free cash flow grew by 8.8%.

The main uses of the free cash flow were dividends (£1.181 billion, up 5.3% from the previous year) and stock buybacks (£1.500 billion, up 50% from the previous year). In total, the company returned £4.85 billion to shareholders through buybacks and dividends over these two years.² While buybacks are a standard mechanism for returning cash to shareholders, high levels of buybacks can also signal that management is not finding productive investment opportunities or is prioritizing short-term share price performance over long-term growth.

Net debt increased by £638 million, leading to a net debt/EBITDA ratio of 2.0x, up from 1.8x at the end of 2024. Historically, RELX targeted a net debt/EBITDA ratio of 2x to 3x, but lately, that range has narrowed to 2x to 2.5x.

RELX's cost structure is divided roughly equally between the cost of staff and the cost of sales (which includes a broad variety of items, including third party software, printing of physical products, energy for data centers, and third-party data purchases). Over the past several years, cost of sales has grown by about 0.5% annually, and staff costs by about 1% annually. Even modest annual headline revenue growth in the 2 to 3% range has been sufficient to drive further margin growth, and that model has held consistently.

² RELX does not disclose the cash flow and tax rate of each specific division. However, as Elsevier contributes about 31% of the operating profit of the company, in the absence of disclosures it is reasonable to attribute about £1.5 billion of these disbursements to the Elsevier business.

STM performance

The STM business of RELX, commonly referred to as Elsevier, is the second largest and the most profitable division by operating margin. In 2025, it performed well, accounting for 28.3% of revenues and 31% of the adjusted operating profit. Underlying revenue growth returned to 5%, a level that was common twenty years ago during the transition to digital distribution of journals. According to management, the growth was driven by sales of research analytics data and tools and by volume growth of articles published (including revenue attributable to Open Access APCs). Article submissions rose by 20% in 2025 and articles published by 10%, above the estimated 8% growth in the global number of articles published.³

Elsevier's adjusted operating profit grew by 7% in 2025, up from 5% growth in 2024 and outpacing revenue growth. The adjusted operating margin reached 38.1% in 2025, up from 37.4% in 2024.

Guidance

RELX does not provide quantitative guidance, leaving investors to draw their own conclusions from qualitative language. Indications of "strong growth" have coincided with underlying growth rates at or above 5%. In its February 2026 results presentation, management projected a year of strong underlying growth in revenue and adjusted operating profit, with margin expansion across every division. For Elsevier, the 2026 guidance is for "good to strong underlying revenue growth with underlying adjusted operating profit growth exceeding underlying revenue growth," which suggests underlying growth should be in the 4 to 5% range with adjusted operating profit growth in the 5 to 7% range. On capital allocation, management announced a further increase in share buybacks to £2.25 billion for 2026, with acquisition spending expected at approximately £250 million, which management projects will raise the net debt/EBITDA to 2.25x.

3 SNG uses 8% growth in the total number of global articles published in discussing their operating performance.

Uncertainties

Investor concerns about RELX center on three AI-related risks. The first is potential revenue loss: businesses like Risk and Legal could see demand affected by competition from new AI services, or by reductions in customer workforces that translate into fewer licenses and subscriptions. The second is margin pressure: reliance on large AI infrastructure providers such as OpenAI and Google creates a dependency on companies whose pricing is expected to rise as they seek to recover substantial capital outlays. The third is cost uncertainty: whether AI will deliver the operational efficiencies management is promising remains unclear, and the transition itself is likely to introduce additional costs before those gains materialize.

Management responded to the concerns in its annual results presentation. Some businesses like Risk have developed their own models, and management argued there are no advantages from switching to those of the leading AI companies. Other businesses like Legal already incorporate AI technology from third parties. Elsevier also expects to deliver significant productivity gains by rolling out LeapSpace, which management believes could expand to the full base of existing Elsevier customers, though uptake is expected to build gradually.⁴

RELX's capital investment has grown steadily over the past decade, rising from £307 million in 2015 to £525 million in 2025. This growth, however, has just kept pace with revenue growth at about 5% of revenues. This benchmark is exactly how RELX and its peers operated twenty years ago. Whether this level of spending proves sufficient as AI reshapes the industry is an open question.

4 CEO Erik Engstrom indicated that "From the new forward-looking LeapSpace launch, which is just recently launched commercially, we can see that it's a significant value uplift to the users. Several of them report very significant time savings or productivity gains or improved results from specific use cases that are very material. We look, therefore, at the potential addressable market as being basically all the institutions that today have any of our platforms in use or any of our subscribers. That order of magnitude is in the thousands, I mean, it's over 10,000 depending on when you want to define it somewhere between 10 and 15,000 institutions. That's potential institutional customers... But we are very positive on the ability for this platform to continue to add value to our customers and meaningfully impact our long-term value add and growth trajectory in this division, but it's going to come through very gradually"
<https://www.relx.com/~media/Files/R/RELX-Group/documents/investors/transcripts/results-2025-transcript.pdf>

SPRINGER NATURE GROUP (SNG)

Share price performance

SNG has a much shorter history as a publicly traded company. It took 13 years and three failed attempts before the company successfully achieved an Initial Public Offering (IPO), debuting on the Frankfurt Stock Exchange on October 4, 2024 at a placement price of €22.50. Since listing, the share price has traded above that placement price for only about 90 days, less than 25% of trading days between October 4, 2024 and March 31, 2026.

TIMELINE OF SPRINGER AND SNG CORPORATE EVENTS

The share price rose as high as €27.38 on December 22, 2024, before a first decline brought it to €16.22 by April 6, 2025, a 40.8% drop. This was steeper than RELX, but similar in timing. Shares recovered through the summer, reaching €23.40 on August 31, 2025, before a second and deeper decline began. The share price fell to a new low of €15.32 on March 8, 2026, a 34.5% decline from the August high, broadly in line with the decline of RELX over the same period.

The early 2025 dip reflected both dollar weakness and the timing of some investments. SNG guided that in 2025 a 5% decline of the dollar would lower pre-tax net profit by €21.8 million. With earnings before taxes of €403.1 million in 2025, investors would have project-

ed that the 12% decline of the dollar would reduce pre-tax earnings by about €52.3 million, or about 13%. Other currencies declined in the same time frame, notably the Japanese yen, but the gap between that projected impact and the 40% share price decline suggest that other factors were at play.⁵

Operating performance

Group performance

SNG showed a good operating performance in 2025. Underlying revenue grew 6.2% and the adjusted operating profit grew 9.2%, bringing the operating profit margin across the company to 28.2%, up from 27.7% in 2024. Operating cash flow increased 3.2%, and free cash flow grew 36%, reflecting both improved operating cash flow and lower interest payments. The main uses of cash were interest payments and lease repayments (€116.9 million) and debt repayment (€294.3 million). Dividend payments of €26.8 million had a limited effect on the cash flow. Debt repayment brought the net debt/EBITDA ratio to 1.7x at the end of 2025, roughly in the middle of the company's target range of 1.5x to 2.0x.

Research performance

Research is the main business of SNG. In 2025, it accounted for 79% of revenues and 89% of the adjusted operating profit. It is also the fastest growing segment, with 7% underlying revenue growth and 10% underlying adjusted operating profit growth. These rates imply gains in both revenue share and operating margin relative to Elsevier. The adjusted operating margin was 32%, up from 31.7% in 2024. Published articles grew 12%, four percentage points above the estimated growth of the global number of articles published.

Historically, Springer had lower revenues per article than Elsevier, although this gap has been narrowing. Elsevier has continued to increase the number of articles it publishes at a faster rate than revenue growth, while Springer has acquired some journals with higher APCs through its merger with Nature Group. Since the cost of publishing articles is roughly comparable across publishers, differences in pricing are the main drivers of differences in profitability.

5 The cashflow impact of currency fluctuations is minimized both by hedging contracts and by the decision by many companies, including SNG, to raise some debt in the currencies of their main markets, in order to match interest payments in local currencies to actual revenues.

Guidance

For 2026, management expects to maintain recent revenue growth and further improve margins. Underlying revenue growth for the entire group should be in the 5 to 6% range and margins should improve by another 0.3 percentage points to 28.5%. No divisional guidance was offered explicitly.

Uncertainties

The investment issues of SNG are slightly different from those of RELX, in large part because of the different make-up of the two companies. RELX has four main businesses, so it is exposed to a broader range of concerns and also needs strategies for AI that look very different depending on the division. On the other hand, SNG's Research division is its primary business, with two much smaller divisions in Health and Education.

Interviews conducted for this report suggest that the AI questions facing SNG's research business are similar to those of Elsevier. Management of SNG has indicated that it believes it can deploy AI to improve researcher productivity tools such as Nature Research Assistant, which is currently in beta testing, in order to improve its financial performance. Management also points to potential uses of AI to improve the operating performance of the business. On the other hand, there are concerns that data processing costs will rise, that replacing traditional costs may be harder or take longer than expected, and that the vast increase in the use of AI in core activities like article writing and peer review may lead to a collapse in the credibility of scientific research communications.

The performance of SNG's two smaller businesses has not kept pace with the Research division. Their scale suggests that they may not be able to compete effectively over time, in contrast with the Research division that is roughly comparable in size to its counterpart at Elsevier (Primary Research). SNG's rate of investment at about 7 to 8% of revenues is higher than the 5% industry benchmark, but its smaller scale is a structural disadvantage relative to larger competitors. Management reduced total investments by 8.8% in 2025, raising questions over the sustainability of SNG's competitive position if investments are capped below what the business requires.

WILEY

Share price performance

In the three years following SPARC's 2021 Landscape Analysis update, Wiley Class A shares⁶ underperformed the S&P 500 significantly. Between October 1, 2021 and September 30, 2024 the share price declined by 7.6% (from \$52.66 to \$48.67), while the S&P 500 grew by 32.3%.

That underperformance continued in the period covered by this report. Between October 1, 2024 to March 31, 2026, Wiley shares declined 21.7% (from \$48.67 to \$38.10), while the S&P 500 rose 14.4%. Like RELX and SNG, this period contained two distinct phases of decline for Wiley. Shares peaked at \$53.11 on November 25, 2024, and fell to \$37.91 by March 4, 2025, a 28.6% decline. Shares then recovered, peaking at \$46.73 on March 10, 2025, before a second and deeper decline brought the price to \$28.79 on February 11, 2026, a 38.4% decline. The share price has since rebounded, closing at \$38.71 on March 31, 2026, a 25.6% increase from the February low.

Operating performance

Group performance

Wiley's financial year runs from May 1 to April 30, which means the period covered by this report spans two partial fiscal years, rather than one full and one partial fiscal year like each of the three other companies.

In 2025, Wiley returned to profitability. The company had closed 2023 in virtual breakeven, with net profit after tax of \$17.2 million (\$0.31 per share). In 2024, the company recorded a loss of \$200.3 million, primarily because of the costs associated with the retraction of over

⁶ Wiley has two classes of shares (Wiley Class A and Wiley Class B). The first one accounts for the bulk of the public float, while the second is designed for insiders and family members in order to maintain control. Class A shares elect 30% of the board and each share has one tenth of a vote for every other matter, while class B shares elect the rest of the board and each share has one vote for every other matter. All data in this document refers to Class A shares.

11,000 Hindawi articles and the subsequent shut down of the imprint, with net revenues declining 7.3%.

In 2025, net revenues continued to decline by a further 8%, but adjusted revenues⁷ grew by 3%. Operating income quadrupled from \$52.2 million to \$221.4 million and net income swung to a profit of \$84.2 million from the \$200.3 million loss in the prior year. With US dollar revenues at 51% of total revenues, the dollar's decline would have generated an estimated currency gain of approximately \$69.13 million after taxes for the financial year ending April 30, 2025.⁸ Against an \$84.2 million net profit, this suggests most of Wiley's swing to profitability reflects currency movements rather than underlying business performance. Meanwhile, EBITDA grew by 8%, earnings per share by 31%, and free cash flow by 10%. Progress has continued in 2026: for the nine months ending January 31, 2026, revenues are virtually flat (-0.5%), operating income is up by 15%, and net income is up fivefold to \$86.3 million, already \$2.1 million above the full-year 2025 figure. Adjusted revenues are flat, EBITDA is up 12% and earnings per share are up 19%.

Cash flow is also improving. After a sharp decline in 2024, when cash from operating activities fell \$69.4 million (-25.1%), 2025 was a year of stabilization, with cash from operating activities declining only 2.4% (-\$5 million) despite revenue decline. Wiley also reduced investments by \$12.6 million (-11.8%) in 2025. For the first nine months of 2026, cash from operating activities has almost doubled, and net investments have added \$45.6 million to cash generated in the current financial year.⁹

The net debt/EBITDA ratio at the end of FY2025 was 1.8x, despite returning 109% of free cash flow to shareholders through dividends and share buybacks. Dividends and share buybacks grew 12.3% in FY2025.

7 Wiley's term for underlying or organic revenues.

8 Wiley does not disclose the expected impact on profits, but highlights the impact after the end of the fiscal year.

9 The positive net cash generation in the first six months is due to a reduction of \$5.6 million in content, technology and equipment investments and \$114.1 million of cash from divestitures (mostly thanks to the proceeds from the sale of the University Services business).

Research performance

Research is Wiley's largest source of both revenues and profits. In 2025, it accounted for 64.8% of revenues and 61.2% of EBITDA.¹⁰ The research business EBITDA margin was 34.7%, up from 31.8% in 2024.

Articles published grew 8%, in line with the market, and article revenue rose 4%. However, total research segment growth was only 3%, reflecting flat revenues in its research solutions business, which Wiley attributed to soft recruitment revenues.¹¹

Guidance

In its FY2025 results presentation on June 17, 2025, management issued initial guidance for FY2026. The key elements of the guidance were low- to mid-single digit revenue growth, an adjusted EBITDA margin of 25.5% to 26.5% (up from 24% in FY2025), adjusted earnings per share of \$3.90 to \$4.35 (up from \$3.64 in FY 2025), and growth of free cash flow from \$126 million in 2025 to approximately \$200 million in 2026.

At the first half report in December 2025, management narrowed its guidance for revenue growth to low single digit growth, effectively a downgrade on revenues but an indication it could adjust its costs to meet other targets. The latest guidance has held the revenue range but upped guidance for the EBITDA margin and the adjusted earnings per share to the higher end of the range. It confirmed free cash flow at approximately \$200 million.

Uncertainties

Wiley's investment uncertainties are more similar to those of SNG than RELX. Wiley's research business is about two thirds the size of SNG's, and scale matters in the transition to large scale AI deployment.

10 Wiley reports divisional EBITDA rather than divisional operating profit (the difference is that the latter metric includes the amortization and depreciation of assets).

11 Wiley operates a network of recruitment businesses in scientific areas of expertise <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/solutions-partnerships/corporates/advertising-solutions/human-resources/>

The cost to launch and maintain AI-based productivity tools is unlikely to differ substantially across Elsevier, SNG and Wiley, but Wiley has less revenues and cash flow to support that investment. In the last year, Wiley spent \$94 million across all categories of investment, while SNG spent €146.6 million (about \$164.8 million). AI Gateway, Wiley's productivity tool, will have to compete both with LeapSpace and Nature Research Assistant, both of which will have access to more content. It will also face competition from other platforms with access to Wiley's content directly, since Wiley has been licensing it aggressively to support revenue growth.

As with Elsevier and SNG, Wiley's reliance on third-party LLMs as the foundation for these services exposes it to cost pressures as AI companies will seek to recoup their investments.

Wiley's Learning division is subject to additional uncertainty from Open Educational Resources and LLMs, which both pose displacement risks to traditional educational and professional materials. SNG faces the same concern, but the heavier weight of Learning revenues and profits at Wiley exacerbates the risk.

CLARIVATE

Share price performance

Clarivate's share price history differs significantly from the other three companies analyzed in this report. In the four and a half years between October 1, 2021 and March 31, 2026, the share price declined 88.2% (from \$21.53 to \$2.53 per share), while the S&P 500 rose 49.8%. From its absolute high of \$33.39 on October 5, 2020, the share price decline reaches 92.4%. By October 2024, Clarivate shares had already declined 67.0% (to \$7.10) over three years, while the S&P 500 had grown 32.3% over the same period.

The decline continued through the 18-month period covered by this report. Between October 1, 2024 and March 31, 2026, Clarivate shares fell 61.6%, the deepest decline in this analysis, while the S&P 500 rose 13.4%. The decline has been almost continuous, with the fluctuations typical of equity markets, but with none of the intermediate recoveries seen at the other three companies.

Several factors appear to be driving the protracted decline: revenue growth has been flat to slightly declining, acquisitions like ProQuest have proved expensive, and multiple management changes have disrupted the company's strategic direction. Investors have recently responded positively to the announced divestiture of the Lifesciences & Healthcare business, though it remains to be seen whether the divestiture will go through and achieve the expected proceeds. In 2025, reports surfaced that Clarivate could divest its Intellectual Property business, but the company now describes that business as "core."

Operating performance

Group performance

The operating performance of Clarivate has been lackluster in recent years. In 2025, organic revenue was virtually flat (a \$3 million decline), with small growth in subscription revenues (\$11 million) more than offset by a \$14 million decline in transactional revenues. Total revenues fell to \$2.445 billion, a \$102 million decline (-4%), mostly reflecting divestitures and disposals with a small offset from the depreciation of the dollar.

Adjusted EBITDA declined 5.5% to \$1.002 billion from \$1.060 billion the previous year. Organic decline accounted for 2.2%, with the balance driven by divestitures and only partially offset by foreign exchange gains.

Cash flow generation was similarly weak. Operating cash flow declined 2.8%, primarily reflecting the EBITDA decline and rising restructuring costs, only partly offset by lower interest payments, cash taxes, and a reduction in net working capital.¹² Capital investments declined by 9% in 2025, a reduction of \$25.9 million, despite expectations around AI. The absolute level of investment (\$263.2 million) equals 10.7% of revenues, double the level of RELX and the typical industry benchmark. However, past concerns about inadequate

investments in the businesses inherited from the Thomson Reuters Science division and from ProQuest make it possible that this spending is to compensate for previous underinvestment as opposed to a deliberate strategy.

The company also carries significant debt. Long-term financial debt at December 31, 2025 was \$4.4 billion (including debt maturing in the next twelve months), only partially offset by \$392 million in cash. The net debt/EBITDA ratio was therefore close to 4.1x, a borderline “healthy” ratio that investors will continue to monitor.¹³

Despite this leverage, the company spent \$224.5 million on stock repurchases in 2025, following \$300 million in repurchases in 2023 and 2024. Fitch rates Clarivate’s bonds as junk bonds (BB-, three levels below investment grade). Two bond repayments of \$900 million each are due in July 2028 and July 2029. The existing bonds have relatively low coupons, and refinancing at higher rates poses a meaningful risk if the promised revenue growth fails to materialize.

Research performance

Research-related activities sit within Clarivate’s Academia & Government (A&G) division. In 2025, A&G accounted for 55.6% of total revenues, with the balance divided between Intellectual Property and Life Sciences & Healthcare. While all these divisions lost revenue in 2025, A&G was the only division to grow organically, by 1.6%. The headline 4.6% revenue decline was driven exclusively by the divestiture of Scholar One, which accounted for a 6.7% decline, partially offset by a 0.5% positive contribution from the depreciation of the dollar.

A&G accounted for 54.7% of adjusted EBITDA in 2025, down 2.8% from 2024. The company does not disclose a divisional revenue mix, so relative weights cannot be determined.

12 An increase in net working capital is a use of cash, while a decrease is a source of cash. Net working capital is the use of cash to build inventory, finance work in progress and extend credit to customers minus sources of capital like advances from customers and other debts (suppliers, taxes).

13 <https://www.jpmorgan.com/insights/banking/commercial-loans-and-lines-of-credit/debt-to-ebitda-calculating-business-borrowing-capacity> It should be noted that there are no “hard rules” for an acceptable ratio, and that management uses of cash are as significant as the ratios themselves.

Management states that 93% of revenues are recurring, substantially lessening the dependence on transactional revenues, which are harder to plan for and subject to economic fluctuations. Clarivate also indicates that 97% of G&A revenues derive from proprietary solutions and argues that these revenues are better protected from AI disruption and should provide a basis for further innovation.

Guidance

Clarivate offered upbeat guidance for 2026 across three main metrics. The first, Annualized Contract Value (ACV) growth, is unique to Clarivate in this report and measures the growth in revenue generated from existing customer contracts, as opposed to acquiring new customers. Clarivate expects to raise ACV by 2.5% in 2026. The second metric is for recurring organic revenue growth of 1.5%, reflecting the company's strategic shift toward recurring revenues and away from transactional ones. The third is for free cash flow of \$400 million, an increase of about \$30 million over 2025.

Uncertainties

As we noted throughout this section, investors have concerns about Clarivate that extend beyond those that affect RELX, SNG, and even Wiley. Investors have fled the stock due to a combination of factors, including management turnover, expensive acquisitions, strategic drift, and a heavy debt load coming due in the next few years. The AI concerns raised for the other companies also apply, with Clarivate's falling EBITDA and high debt load leaving it in a potentially weaker position to invest in an AI transition.

DATA TABLES

Table 1: Highest and Lowest Closing Share Prices Q4 2024 to Q1 2025

Company	Currency	Highest	Lowest	% Change
RELX	British Pounds	41.35	35.82	-13.4%
SNG	Euros	27.38	16.22	-40.8%
Wiley	US Dollars	53.13	37.91	-28.6%
Clarivate	US Dollars	6.83	3.93	-42.5%

Table 2: Highest and Lowest Share Prices Q3 2025 to Q1 2026

Company	Currency	Highest	Lowest	% Change
RELX	British Pounds	41.23	20.13	-51.2%
SNG	Euros	23.50	14.92	-36.5%
Wiley	US Dollars	43.51	29.07	-33.2%
Clarivate	US Dollars	4.53	1.68	-62.9%

Table 3: Underlying/Organic Revenue Growth 2025 (%)

Company	RELX	SNG	Wiley*	Clarivate
Revenue Growth	7%	6.20%	3%	-0.10%

* First four months of calendar year 2025; +1% in Q1 2026 and -1% in Q2 2026 (covering the the next seven months of 2025)

Table 4: Group Operating Margin (or EBITDA) 2023-25

Company	Financial Metric	2023	2024	2025
RELX	Adjusted Operating Profit	33.1%	33.9%	34.8%
SNG	Adjusted Operating Profit	NA	27.7%	28.2%
Wiley	Adjusted EBITDA Margin	23.3%	22.8%	24.0%
Clarivate	Adjusted EBITDA Margin	42.5%	41.5%	40.8%

Table 5: Research Division Operating Margin (or EBITDA) 2023-25

Company	Division	Financial Metric	2023	2024	2025
RELX	STM (Elsevier)	Adjusted Operating Profit	38.0%	37.4%*	38.1%
SNG	Research	Adjusted Operating Profit	—	31.7%	32.1%
Wiley	Research	Adjusted EBITDA Margin	34.9%	31.8%	34.7%
Clarivate	A&G	Adjusted EBITDA Margin	42.2%	42.5%	43.3%

* 2024 restated (originally 38.4%)

Table 6: Free Cash Flow Growth 2024-2025 (millions)

Company	Currency	2024	2025	% change
RELX	British Pounds	2,126	2,313	9%
SNG	Euros	218.6	297.8	36%
Wiley*	US Dollars	114	126	11%
Clarivate	US Dollars	358	365	2%

* First four months of calendar year 2025

Table 7: Net Debt/EBITDA Ratio at the End of FY 2024 and 2025

Company	2024	2025
RELX	1.8	2.0
SNG	2.3	1.7
Wiley*	2.0	1.7
Clarivate	4.1	4.1

* End of January 2025 and 2026 due to Wiley's different fiscal year

Table 8: Capital Investment in Absolute Value 2023-25 (millions)

Company	Currency	2023	2024	2025	% change 2025 vs. 2024
RELX	British Pounds	477	484	525	8.5%
SNG	Euros	177.7	160.8	146.6	-8.8%
Wiley	US Dollars	98.4	106.6	94.0	-11.8%
Clarivate	US Dollars	243	289	263	-9.0%

Table 9: Capital Investment as a Percentage of Revenues 2025

Company	RELX	SNG	Wiley	Clarivate
Capital investment as % of revenue	5.5%	7.6%	5.6%	10.7%

Table 10: Guidance for 2026

Company	Revenue growth	Margin growth	Free cash flow growth
RELX	No quantitative targets. Expects "strong growth in underlying revenues and operating profit"		
SNG	5-6% (underlying)	30 basis points (underlying)	—
Wiley	Low single digits (adjusted)	25.5 to 26.5% adjusted EBITDA margin	Approximately \$200 million (vs. 126 in 2025)
Clarivate	1.5% (recurring revenues)	41.5%	Approximately \$400 million (vs. 365 in 2025)

GLOSSARY OF FINANCIAL TERMS

Adjusted Cash Flow The cash actually generated by the operations of the company, adjusted to reflect capital investments and the growth or decline of the working capital.

EBITDA Margin EBITDA margin is the ratio between the EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization) and revenues. EBITDA is a measure of the profitability of a company excluding the impact of its capital structure (i.e. how much interest is paid) and of tax policies (the taxes paid, and also the tax policies affecting depreciation and amortization).

Free Cash Flow The adjusted cash flow after the payment of taxes, interest and expenditures - or proceeds - for acquisitions or divestitures.

FTSE 100 The FTSE 100 is a market capitalization-weighted Index of the 100 largest companies traded on the London Stock Exchange. The FTSE 100 is often used by investors as a benchmark to assess the share price performance of individual companies against its peers. See this [fact sheet](#) for more details.

MSCI World Index The MSCI World Index is a market capitalization-weighted index of about 1300 large and medium cap stocks across 23 countries and is used to provide a benchmark for the performance of stocks across all developed markets. See this [fact sheet](#) for more details.

Net Debt/EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization) is a measure of the amount of financial leverage of a company. Companies can have different philosophies about how much debt to carry: more debt leads to higher risk in case of a downturn in the business and/or a spike in interest rates; on the other hand, more debt means that there is more cash available to reward equity shareholders, since the cost of debt is typically

tax deductible, ending up costing less than equity as a source of capital for a company.

Operating Margin

Operating Margin is the ratio between Operating Profit (revenues minus costs, including depreciation and amortization) and revenues.

Placement Price

Placement price is the price of the shares when they are sold to new investors in preparation of an IPO or a capital increase.

S&P 500

The S&P 500 is a market capitalization weighted Index of 500 of the largest US traded companies. The S&P 500 is often used by investors as a benchmark to assess the share price performance of individual companies against its peers. For more information, see these [fact sheets](#).

Underlying

“Underlying” and “organic” are interchangeable terms used in companies’ presentations to provide investors with a picture of the performance of a company that is not affected by some factors that will affect their “headline” results:

- The adjustments that are included in the translation from headline to organic (or underlying) growth represent the results as they would have been without changes in exchange rates over the reported period and without the impact of acquisitions and divestitures completed in the previous 12 months
- Some companies also take out results associated with assets “held for sale” (i.e. assets that will be divested but have not been yet sold)
- Finally, companies will often provide “adjusted” operating profits, where the “adjustments” are typically adding back to the operating profit the cost of one off, non-recurring charges. Some companies stretch the boundaries of this type of adjustment by adding back restructuring charges (i.e. the costs associated primarily with terminating employees in large numbers and also reducing associated or eliminating associated costs such as benefits or real estate leases).

June 2026

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<https://doi.org/10.82513/px9c-q310>

